

PRINCIPAL LEADERSHIP PRACTICES AND KINDER-TEACHER COMMITMENT IN NABUNTURAN EAST DISTRICT

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Abstract. This study examined the relationship between the leadership practices of Principals and the professional commitment of Kinder-Teachers in Nabunturan District, Davao De Oro Schools Division. The research design used was non-experimental descriptive-correlational, and an adapted survey instrument was used to collect responses from randomly selected teacher-respondents. The study found that the extent of the Principal's leadership practices in resource allocation, collaboration beyond school, and monitoring progress was often demonstrated. However, teacher leadership and data-driven practices were only occasionally demonstrated. Similarly, the professional commitment of Kinder-Teachers in terms of advocacy, parent engagement, continuous learning, and adaptability was often demonstrated, while curriculum development was only occasionally demonstrated. The study found a significant relationship between Principal's leadership practices and Kinder-Teacher's Professional Commitment. All domains of Principal's leadership practices significantly influenced Kinder-Teacher's Professional Commitment. Future research may investigate the long-term impact of enhanced leadership practices on teacher commitment and student outcomes

KEY WORDS

1. Principal's leadership practices.
2. Kinder Teacher Commitment.

1. Introduction

Principals play a vital role in shaping the success of schools through their leadership practices. Instructional leadership is key to their effectiveness, as it involves setting high expectations for teaching and learning, promoting collaboration among staff, and monitoring student progress. However, there are challenges to balancing administrative duties with instructional leadership responsibilities, addressing diverse needs, navigating external pressures, and promoting equity and inclusion. Effective principal leadership requires interpersonal skills, strategic decision-making, and ongoing professional growth. By prioritizing students' needs and fostering a positive school climate, principals can drive positive outcomes for all. Umar et al. (2021) examined the effectiveness of principal leadership practices in secondary schools located in Niger State, Nigeria. The authors found that the extent of principal leadership practices and school effectiveness attributes in secondary schools in Niger State is high. However, the country focuses mainly on issues other than leadership practices, such as training programs for secondary school teachers to enhance school effectiveness. The concept highlights the

need for secondary school principals to identify and promote the professional development needs of teachers, ensuring that teachers are effectively trained to enhance the development of secondary schools into centers of excellence.

Education reform drives changes in principal leadership. Instructional coaching is a common tool, but results are inconsistent. Little is known about how principals use leadership to establish effective coaching. Sandlin (2022) found that principals who were former coaches use effective leadership practices that positively influence coaching. This idea can enhance principals' practices to support teachers better, leading to positive social change. District leaders may need to provide training to ensure consistent implementation of coaching to support teachers and improve student success. Kaegi (2022) researched the connection between principal leadership practices and teacher morale in rural Southern Illinois. The study observed elementary, middle, and high schools with students from Pre-K to grade twelve. The research revealed Model the Way and Rapport with Teachers as the most prevalent leadership practices. The study found a link between leadership practices and teacher morale, with the most significant response rates observed in the aforementioned practices. Shared perceptions of teachers and principals on principal leadership were also crucial in maintaining high teacher morale. In the Philippine setting, the trend of principal leadership is gaining momentum as a powerful vehicle for educational improvement. Educators nationwide increasingly recognize the value of collaboration, data-driven decision-making, and reflective practice in enhancing teaching and learning outcomes (Cansoy et al., 2022). Schools and educational institutions are actively adopting PLCs as a framework for professional development, allowing teachers to come together to discuss curriculum, share best

practices, and analyze student data. This trend is in line with the Philippines' commitment to improving the quality of education, as stated in the K-12 Basic Education Program and other national initiatives. Additionally, this has led to a faster adoption of digital platforms, which has made it easier for educators to engage, share ideas, and access resources. As this trend continues to grow, it has the potential to positively impact the Philippine education system, promoting a culture of continuous improvement and excellence in teaching and learning (Liu, 2023). Principal Leadership offers significant promise for educational improvement in the Philippines, but several challenges persist. One notable challenge is resource constraints, particularly in public schools. Additionally, the country's geographical diversity and the dispersed nature of many schools make it challenging to establish effective leadership, especially in remote or rural areas (Freeman, 2023). Like in many educational settings, kindergarten teachers in Davao de Oro province face a range of concerns and challenges. These concerns often revolve around adapting to diverse student needs, aligning curriculum with national standards, limited access to resources and professional development opportunities, and the need for effective teaching strategies tailored to young learners. Leadership of a school head promising avenue is to address these concerns. Kindergarten teachers in Davao de Oro, can engage in collaborative efforts to develop and share best practices, discuss innovative teaching strategies suitable for their specific context, and collectively work towards curriculum alignment, given the support of the School Principal, who provides a supportive network where educators can share resources, advocate for improved resource allocation, and access ongoing professional development opportunities.

2. Methodology

This chapter outlines the processes and steps involved in conducting the study. It covers the study design selection, the respondents and the sampling method, the research instruments used to gather data, the procedures followed, ethical considerations, and data analysis. These steps are essential to ensure the appropriateness and correctness of the data collection, analysis, and interpretation, which are necessary to produce reliable results.

2.1. Research Design—The study used the non-experimental, descriptive-correlational research design, which is a non-experimental design that investigates the degree to which two or more variables are related. It does not involve the manipulation of any variables but rather measures and analyses the existing relationship between them (Creswell, 2014). In this study, correlational research design can be used to examine the relationship between the extent of principal leadership practices and kinder-teacher commitment. According to Creswell (2014), a descriptive-correlational research design describes and explains the relationship between two or more variables. The main goal of this type of research design is to identify the relationship between variables, and it can be used to make predictions about future events. Descriptive-correlational research designs are used to describe the relationships between variables. Researchers collect data on two or more variables and then analyze the data to determine if there is a relationship between them. This type of research is used to generate hypotheses for future studies (Campbell Stanley, 1963). Finally, a descriptive-correlational research design can be valuable in situations where experimental manipulation of variables is not possible or ethical. For example, it may be unethical to manipulate variables such as age, gender, or medical condition in order to examine their effects on other variables. In such cases, a descriptive-correlational design can provide a valuable alternative for investigating the relationships between variables of interest, without requiring manipulation or control of those variables. In

this study, the relationship between the principal's leadership practices in the professional learning community and the Kinder-Teacher's professional commitment in Nabunturan District is assumed to have an association; thus, the research design's measure is appropriate for this study.

2.2. Research Respondents—Respondents of the study were the Kinder Teachers and Elementary School Teachers of Nabunturan District, Davao de Oro Schools Division. She used the Raosoft sample size calculator, where a total of 120 respondents were taken randomly from each respective School within the Elementary Schools of the Nabunturan District. One randomly determined, the respondents were informed through online platform and face-to-face considering the availability of the Wifi Connections; they were likewise oriented about the purpose and importance of the study and its contribution to their professional development status. These teacher-respondents were the elementary teachers who were actively and directly involved in most of the curriculum-related school's activities relevant to effective curriculum management and delivery through learning action cell sessions where learners' performance most especially Key Stage 1 and other related activities to support the learners and likewise to support programs, projects and activities in line with the implementation plan as directed by DepED mandates under MATATAG Agenda. Moreover, teachers with skills in strategizing the simplification of operational processes and management in school, apart from curriculum implementation and delivery, are likewise trying

to improve the system to achieve performance given learning standards and professional development among teachers. They are qualified for they are expected to have performed and contributed to the betterment of the schools and the parents' participation given the new normal learning system during SY 2023-2024. Further, they have frequently engaged in various seminars and trainings in the school management and curriculum development delivery system. Moreover, assumptions in the respective schedule of classes during data collection were explicitly discussed with the respondents, and even observance of health protocol was strictly implemented based on Executive Order 31 S 2020 to avoid possible and lower the risk of contamination.

2.3. *Research Instrument*—This research study used the adapted instrument taken from reviewed literature and related studies. The researcher took time to gather and read reviews of related literature to come up with concepts for the content that support the instrument and its corresponding strands in articulating the set of question items, reducing threats to validity.

Items were adapted from the contents of the reviewed literature as argued by the authors. There were two parts of the survey questionnaire, which consisted of the Principal's leadership practices in the professional learning community in terms of teacher leadership, resource allocation, data-driven, collaboration beyond school, and monitoring progress. Likewise, the second part of the survey measured the extent of Kinder-Teacher professional commitment in terms of continuous learning, curriculum development, adaptability, parent engagement, and advocacy. Further, the survey statements were subjected to a test-retest or validity and reliability testing using Cronbach Alpha at a .05 level of confidence and generated an alpha Cronbach of 0.869, which means that 86.9 percent level of confidence in the validity and reliability of the survey statement constructs (Pallant 2010). The questionnaire used a 5-point Likert scale to determine the extent Principal's Leadership practices on Professional Learning Community; the scale, descriptive rating, and interpretation are provided below:

Scale, Descriptive Rating, and Interpretation

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The principal leadership practices are always manifested
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The principal leadership practices are often-times manifested
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The principal leadership practices are sometimes manifested
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The principal leadership practices are rarely manifested
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The principal leadership practices are not manifested

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—Conducting a study involves a series of critical steps, including obtaining permission in an ethical

manner. This step is crucial to uphold the core principles of respect, transparency, and responsible research conduct. The statements in this re-

Scale, Descriptive Rating, and Interpretation

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The kinder-teacher commitment is always manifested
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The kinder-teacher commitment is often-times manifested
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The kinder-teacher commitment is sometimes manifested
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The kinder-teacher commitment is rarely manifested
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The kinder-teacher commitment is not manifested

gard are based on the policies and guidelines of Rizal Memorial Colleges. As part of the request, researchers must explain their intentions for data collection, analysis, and dissemination, and how they align with the overall research goals. If there are any concerns or questions anticipated from recipients, they should be addressed promptly. This correspondence should address any concerns or questions anticipated from recipients, alongside assurances regarding ethical safeguards, confidentiality measures, and the study’s potential benefits. The formal permission request is then made, explicitly seeking authorization to proceed and emphasizing the significance of their support for the research’s success. Permission to conduct the study. On December 2023, before collecting data, the researcher must obtain permission from the appropriate authorities, such as the research adviser and the Dean of the Rizal Memorial Colleges and the top management of DepEd Davao de Oro Schools Division through channel. This permission-seeking process typically involves submitting a research proposal that includes information about the study design, procedures, and potential risks and benefits. The researcher provided information about the purpose and goals of the study, and how the data will be

collected, analyzed, and reported. In addition, on January 2024 the researcher ensured that all participants are fully informed about the study and their rights, and that they provide informed consent before participating. Distribution and retrieval of the questionnaire. First week of February 2024, the researcher ensured the accuracy and completeness of data, the distribution and retrieval of questionnaires were conducted in a standardized and systematic manner. She went into considering the following conditions: Identifying the target population: On December 2023, the researcher identified the appropriate target population of the study, and ensure that the questionnaire is distributed only to individuals who meet the inclusion criteria. The researcher obtained informed consent from all participants before distributing the questionnaire. The researcher ensured that the questionnaire is anonymous, meaning that respondents are not identified by name or other personal information. The researcher also ensured that the data collected is kept confidential and only used for the purposes of the study. On January 2024, randomly selected respondents were given sufficient time to complete the questionnaire and were allowed to ask any questions they may have about the process. The researcher collected

the completed questionnaires in a timely and organized manner, to ensure that data is not lost or misplaced.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—Mean scores and standard deviation were used to address statement problems posed in number one (1) extent of the principal’s leadership practices, and statement problem number two (2) on the extent of Kinder-Teacher’s commitment in Nabunturan District, Davao de Oro Schools Division. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient or Pearson-r was used to determine its strength/direction significant relationship between the principal’s leadership practices and Kinder-Teacher’s commitment. Simple Linear Regression analysis was used to address statement problem number 4, on the indicators of Principal’s leadership practices that significantly influence Kinder-Teacher’s commitment (Pallant, 2000) and (Gujarati, 2000). All data processing and analysis were performed using Jeffrey’s Statistics Amazing Program (JASP) version 0.12.20. Discussions and interpretations followed when results yielded.

3. Results and Discussion

In this chapter, the researcher addresses the collection of data and its subsequent presentation, analysis, and interpretation. Both tabular and textual formats are employed to enhance the depth of analysis and facilitate the extraction of meaningful implications. Additionally, these presentations serve as supporting evidence for the hypothesis put forth.

Table 1 shows the summary of the extent of the Principal’s leadership practices. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: resource allocation (3.62), collaboration beyond school (3.57), and monitoring progress (3.45) are oftentimes manifested, while teacher-leadership (3.38) and data-driven (3.37) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.47 denotes the extent of learning action cell sessions is oftentimes manifested, thus, extensive.

Table 1. Principal’s Leadership Practices and Mean Descriptive Equivalent

No	Principal’s Leadership Practices	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Teacher-Leadership	3.38	Moderately Extensive
2	Resource Allocation	3.62	Extensive
3	Data-Driven	3.37	Moderately Extensive
4	Collaboration Beyond School	3.57	Extensive
5	Monitoring Progress	3.45	Extensive
Overall Mean		3.47	Extensive

The extent of a principal’s leadership practices profoundly shapes the overall school environment and directly influences the success of both educators and students. Effective school leadership involves a multifaceted approach that encompasses instructional leadership, organizational management, and the cultivation of a positive school culture. Principals who prioritize in-

structional leadership actively engage in curriculum development, instructional strategies, and teacher professional development to enhance the quality of education. They create an environment that fosters continuous learning and encourages teachers to innovate in their teaching methods. Organizational management skills are also crucial, as principals need to efficiently allocate resources, manage budgets, and ensure a smooth operation of day-to-day activities (Filderman, et.al., (2023). Moreover, Meyer, Richter and Hartung-Beck (2022) said that a principal’s role in shaping a positive school

culture cannot be overstated. Successful leaders promote a collaborative and inclusive atmosphere, where communication is open, and the contributions of all stakeholders are valued. The extent of a principal’s leadership practices is reflected in the overall academic performance, morale of the school community, and the development of a learning environment that prepares students for success in a rapidly changing world. Continuous self-reflection, professional development, and adaptability are key components of effective leadership practices that contribute to the sustained growth and success of a school.

Table 2 shows a summary of the extent of Kinder-Teacher’s Commitment. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators, which are as follows: advocacy (3.91), parent engagement (3.87), continuous learning (3.46), and adaptability (3.43) are of-

ten manifested, while curriculum development (2.99) is sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.53 denotes the extent to which Kinder-Teacher’s Professional Commitment is oftentimes manifested, thus being extensive.

Table 2. Kinder-Teacher’s Commitment and Mean Descriptive Equivalent

No	Kinder-Teacher’s Commitment	Mean Descriptive Equivalent
1	Continuous Learning	3.46 Extensive
2	Curriculum Development	2.99 Moderately Extensive
3	Adaptability	3.43 Extensive
4	Parent Engagement	3.87 Extensive
5	Advocacy	3.91 Extensive
Overall Mean		3.53 Extensive

The extent of a kindergarten teacher’s professional commitment plays a pivotal role in shaping the early educational experiences of young learners. Meredith et.al. (2023) shared that beyond the traditional responsibilities of imparting academic knowledge, kindergarten teachers are entrusted with the foundational task of fostering a positive and supportive learning environment. A highly committed kindergarten teacher demonstrates passion for early childhood education, dedicating time and effort to create engaging and developmentally appropri-

ate lesson plans that cater to the unique needs of each child. Professional commitment in this context extends beyond the classroom, involving collaboration with parents and caregivers to ensure a seamless connection between home and school. Moreover, a committed kindergarten teacher stays abreast of the latest pedagogical research and methodologies, striving for continuous improvement in teaching practices. Patience, empathy, and adaptability are integral components of a teacher’s commitment to the holistic development of young minds. Ul-

timately, the extent of a kindergarten teacher’s professional commitment is reflected not only in the students’ academic progress but also in the

nurturing of a lifelong love for learning and a positive attitude toward education (Rickert and Skinner, 2022).

Significant Relationship between Principal’s leadership practices and Kinder-Teacher’s Commitment

Table 3 revealed the yielded results of the significant relationship between the Principal’s leadership practices and the Kinder-Teacher’s Commitment. It provides information that the posed null hypothesis, stating that there is no significant relationship between a Principal’s

leadership practices and Kinder-Teacher’s Commitment, must be rejected for it provided empirical evidence to show its correlation. It can be depicted that Pearson’s Correlation generated a significantly strong positive correlation ($r=0.897$) between the Principal’s leadership practices ($p<.000$) and Kinder-Teacher’s Commitment.

Table 3. Significant Relationship between Principal’s Leadership Practices and Kinder-Teacher’s Commitment

Variables	r-value	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Kinder-Teacher’s Commitment	0.897	< 0.000	Significant	Reject H_0

[*] significant @ $p < 0.05$.

Perfect Positive Correlation ($r = 1.0$); Strong Positive Correlation ($0.7 \leq r < 1.0$); Moderate Positive Correlation ($0.3 \leq r < 0.7$); Weak Positive Correlation ($0 < r < 0.3$); No Correlation ($r = 0$)

The significant relationship between a principal’s leadership practices and a kindergarten teacher’s commitment is crucial in shaping the overall quality of early childhood education. Jerdborg (2023) said that a principal’s leadership practices, encompassing instructional leadership, organizational management, and the cultivation of a positive school culture, directly impact the working conditions and morale of kindergarten teachers. When a principal demonstrates strong instructional leadership by providing support for professional development and fostering a culture of continuous learning, it contributes to the kindergarten teacher’s sense of efficacy and professional growth (Philander, 2021). Zhang, Huang and Ye (2023) shared that effective organizational management by the

principal ensures that teachers have the necessary resources and a well-structured environment, enabling them to focus on teaching and student engagement. Additionally, a positive school culture fostered by the principal, characterized by open communication, collaboration, and shared goals, enhances the kindergarten teacher’s job satisfaction and commitment to the educational mission (Filderman, et.al., (2023). The principal’s leadership practices, therefore, serve as a catalyst for the professional commitment of kindergarten teachers, creating an environment that values their contributions, encourages innovation, and ultimately translates into a higher quality early education experience for young learners (Meyer, Bendikson and Le Fevre, 2023).

Domains of Principal’s Leadership Practices Significantly Influence Kinder-Teacher’s Commitment

Table 4 depicts the simple regression coefficient analysis on domains of Principal’s leadership practices significantly influence Kinder-Teacher’s Commitment. Domains of Principal’s leadership practices in terms of teacher leadership (0.001), resource allocation (0.010), data-driven (0.002), collaboration beyond school

(0.000) and monitoring progress (0.000) significantly influenced Kinder-Teacher’s Professional Commitment. Meanwhile, the R2 value of 0.879 suggests that Kinder-Teacher’s Commitment can be explained by 87.9%. In addition, the F-value shows all the sums of squares, given regression being the model and Residual being the error. The F-value (254.588) and F-statistic is significant $p < 0.010$, indicating that the model better predicts Kinder-Teacher’s Commitment.

Table 4. Regression Coefficient Analysis on Domains of Principal’s Leadership Practices Significantly Influencing Kinder-Teacher’s Commitment

Model	Variable	B	Beta	Standard Error	p-value
H	(Intercept)	4.145	0.079	60.416	0.001
H	(Intercept)	0.313	0.175	1.066	0.270
	Teacher Leadership	0.807	0.107	0.102	0.315
	Resource Allocation	0.441	0.108	0.136	0.196
	Data Driven	0.202	0.097	0.210	0.038
	Collaboration Beyond School	0.921	0.508	0.136	0.296
	Monitoring Progress	0.502	0.057	0.210	0.038
R2	= 0.879				
F-value	= 254.588				
p-value	= < 0.010				

[*] Significant @ $p < 0.05$.

Zhang, Huang, and Ye (2023) say the domains of a principal’s leadership practices have a profound influence on a kindergarten teacher’s professional commitment across various crucial aspects of early childhood education. Firstly, in the domain of instructional leadership, a principal’s guidance and support in pedagogical approaches, curriculum development, and teacher training significantly impact the kindergarten teacher’s commitment to delivering high-quality education. When principals actively engage in promoting effective teaching methods, it fosters a sense of professional efficacy among teachers. Organizational management, another critical domain, directly affects a kindergarten teacher’s

commitment by ensuring that the school’s resources are effectively allocated, creating an environment conducive to teaching and learning. Adequate resources, well-structured classrooms, and efficient administrative support contribute to the teacher’s ability to focus on their primary role of facilitating children’s learning experiences (Meyer, Bendikson and Le Fevre, 2023). The domains of a principal’s leadership practices profoundly influence a kindergarten teacher’s professional commitment across various crucial aspects of early childhood education. Firstly, in the domain of instructional leadership, a principal’s guidance and support in pedagogical approaches, curriculum development, and

teacher training significantly impact the kindergarten teacher's commitment to delivering high-quality education. When principals actively engage in promoting effective teaching methods, it fosters a sense of professional efficacy among teachers (Filderman, et.al., (2023). Organizational management, another critical domain, directly affects a kindergarten teacher's commitment by ensuring that the school's resources are effectively allocated, creating an environment conducive to teaching and learning. Adequate resources, well-structured classrooms, and efficient administrative support contribute to the teacher's ability to focus on their primary role of facilitating children's learning experiences (Tran, Nguyen, HO, Bui and Hoang, 2022).

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter presents the findings, conclusion and recommendation based on the results of the data analyzed, discussed, and drawn implications. Findings are based on the posed statement of the problem; conclusions are based on the findings generated and recommendations are based on the implications of the discussions

4.1. Findings—The following are the findings of the study given the results in the presentation, analysis, and discussions. The extent of the Principal's leadership practices in resource allocation, collaboration beyond school, and monitoring progress is often manifested, while teacher leadership and data-driven practices are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating denotes the extent of learning action cell sessions, which is often extensive. The extent of Kinder-Teacher's Commitment in terms of advocacy, parent engagement, continuous learning, and adaptability is often manifested, while curriculum development is sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating denotes the extent of Kinder-Teacher's Professional Commitment, which is often manifested and thus extensive. There is a significant correlation between a Principal's leadership practices and the kindergarten teacher's commitment. Domains of Principal's leadership practices, such as teacher leadership, resource allocation, data-driven, collaboration beyond school, and monitoring progress (0.000), significantly influenced Kinder-Teacher's commitment.

4.2. Conclusions—Given the findings of the study presented, the following are the conclusions, to wit; The extent of the Principal's

leadership practices in terms of resource allocation, collaboration beyond school, and monitoring progress is often manifested, while teacher leadership and data visualization are sometimes manifested. This denotes the extent of learning action cell sessions, which is often extensive. The extent of Kinder-Teacher's Commitment in terms of advocacy, parent engagement, continuous learning, and adaptability are oftentimes manifested, while curriculum development is sometimes manifested. This denotes the extent of Kinder-Teacher's Professional Commitment is oftentimes manifested, thus, extensive. Pearson's Correlation generated a significant correlation between the Principal's leadership practices and Kinder-Teacher's Commitment. The domains of Principals' leadership practices, in terms of teacher leadership, resource allocation, data-driven, collaboration beyond school, and monitoring progress, significantly influenced Kinder-Teacher's Commitment. Effective leadership is necessary for the advancement of teachers as well as society. In the technological advancement of the 21st century, there are many challenges to compete, including worldwide teacher networks, which demand a great educational leader for educational institutions (Sung-tong, 2007; Abbas et al., 2020). Applying lead-

ership theory to studying school principal leadership practices and kindergarten teacher commitment offers valuable insights into fostering a positive and supportive educational environment. As leaders within the school community, principals can benefit from understanding various leadership theories to effectively guide and motivate their teaching staff.

4.3. Recommendations—With the presented conclusions of the study, the following are recommendations, to wit; Public School District Supervisor. The district may consider implementing professional development programs that focus on enhancing instructional leadership skills. These programs should aim to empower school principals with effective strategies for supporting kindergarten teachers and fostering a culture of continuous learning and innovation. Additionally, collaboration with educational experts and peer-sharing initiatives could contribute to the overall improvement of leadership practices within the district. School Principal. May consider strategic emphasis on organizational management, ensuring that resources are allocated efficiently to create an optimal learning environment for both students and teachers. Principals should prioritize the provision of adequate teaching materials, class-

room infrastructure, and administrative support to enhance the overall teaching experience. Furthermore, fostering a positive school culture through open communication and collaborative decision-making will contribute to a supportive atmosphere that boosts teacher morale and commitment. Teacher. May suggests active participation in ongoing professional development opportunities to stay abreast of the latest pedagogical research and methodologies. Collaborative efforts among teachers, facilitated by the school leadership, can provide a platform for sharing best practices and innovative teaching methods. Additionally, cultivating a sense of shared purpose and collaboration within the teaching staff can contribute to a positive school culture.

Future Researcher. May explore of the long-term impact of enhanced leadership practices on teacher commitment and student outcomes. Research in this area can contribute valuable insights into the sustained effectiveness of leadership interventions and their broader implications for the quality of early childhood education. Continuous investigation and analysis will contribute to the ongoing improvement of leadership practices and their impact on the educational landscape.

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